

Implementing FAIR metrics and assessments for the Earth and Environmental Sciences

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Although there has been great acceptance across disciplines for years to make research data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable), there is still no consensus in most communities on how to implement this concretely on a discipline-specific basis. Available metrics are exclusively domain agnostic, and there are few approaches to formulate binding metrics and tests specifically for particular domains (e.g. earth and environmental science disciplines) and to implement them in assessment tools.

In this presentation, we will introduce new approaches being developed in the FAIR-IMPACT project, based on domain specific use case partners and their communities, including those from the earth and environmental sciences (e.g. collaboration with the communities involved in the FAIR-EASE project), to extend and thus adapt existing FAIR metrics for assessing data objects and the F-UJI FAIR Assessment Tool to more fully incorporate the disciplinary, 'geo' context. A particular focus here will be on incorporating geo-specific metadata standards, covering data formats and semantic artefacts within FAIR metrics, and the detection or verification of these standards by the F-UJI FAIR Assessment Tool.

We will finally report also on the collaboration with one of the EIDA Data Centers (as part of the European Infrastructure for seismic waveform data in EPOS) where the F-UJI FAIR Assessment Tool has been further developed to be aware of the very domain specific standard data and metadata as well as services.

How to cite: Huber, R., Pierkot, C., Vernet, M., and Strollo, A.: Implementing FAIR metrics and assessments for the Earth and Environmental Sciences, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 23–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-8006, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-8006>, 2023.